

E5.2.2: Initial design of data aggregation for self-optimization processes on network operations v1.0

Fecha de Publicación: 31/12/2023

[6GENABLERS-AI]
[6GENABLERS]

**Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión – 6G
I+D**

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	PT2
Líder del PT	i2CAT
Editor Principal	Hatim Chergui
Contribuyentes	Shuaib Siddiqui
Nivel de diseminación	PU
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación	
PU	Publico
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CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo	
PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta
OT	Otro

	Histórico de versiones del documento			
versión	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios
v1.0	Hatim Chergui	Submitted	31/12/2023	

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4 List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BSON	Binary JSON
CDR	Call Detail Records
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
ETL	Extract Load Transform
EC-CDF	Empirical Complementary Cumulative Distribution Function
HDFS	Hadoop Distributed File System
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	Life-cycle Management
MA-DRL	Multi-Agent Deep Reinforcement Learning
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
VNF	Virtual Network Function
OTLP	OpenTelemetry Protocol
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SoA	State-of-the-Art
TSM	Time-Structured Merge
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications

5 Executive Summary

This deliverable summarizes the works carried out in task A5.2 of the project 6GENABLERS, IA para 6G: Ultra Automatización y Optimización, reference number TSI-063000-2021-10, which investigates aggregation methods for 6G network optimisation based on smart telemetry. After a brief introduction, the report recalls the concept of data aggregation and the underlying types while providing concrete examples from OpenTelemetry and MongoDB. The deliverable then reviews literature in terms of data pipelines concept and generic architecture building blocks as well as the corresponding software stack. Additionally, it identifies the requirements of the target aggregation solution in terms of alignment with OpenTelemetry, support of statistical aggregation and openness and performs a detailed comparative study between two well-known aggregation databases, namely InfluxDB and MongoDB and justifies the technical choice of InfluxDB. Moreover, the report addresses the need of statistical data aggregation in 6G network optimisation, and describes two aggregation functions, namely, the EC-CDF and percentile given their importance in 6G optimisation, while providing python code snippets to calculate them from InfluxDB. Finally, the deliverable presents the initial design of the monitoring, aggregation, and decision closed-loop, which interconnects the metric collector, the observability API, InfluxDB-based data aggregation, the resource scaling agent and the holoportation app VNF.

6 Introduction

In the impending era of 6G networks, where the provision of holoportation services is anticipated to be a prominent facet, the optimization of network performance assumes paramount significance. The dynamic and interconnected nature of 6G networks necessitates a comprehensive approach to data monitoring and aggregation. OpenTelemetry, as an instrumental framework, assumes a pivotal role in this context, facilitating the systematic collection of telemetry data from a diverse array of devices and systems.

The utilization of observability APIs becomes imperative, acting as a conduit for seamless integration with monitoring and analytics tools. This integration allows for the extraction of nuanced insights from the copious telemetry data, which is subsequently stored in InfluxDB, a specialized time-series database designed to accommodate the temporal intricacies inherent in network performance metrics. The application of advanced statistical aggregation methodologies becomes paramount, enabling the extraction of discernible patterns and trends from the voluminous and temporally variant data streams, thereby affording a granular understanding of network behavior.

At the forefront of optimization strategies lies the integration of multi-agent deep reinforcement learning, a paradigm that endows the network with intelligent decision-making capabilities. These agents, driven by machine learning algorithms, navigate the complex terrain of 6G networks to dynamically adjust resource allocations and scaling actions in response to evolving conditions. This closed-loop management system orchestrates a symbiotic relationship between OpenTelemetry, observability APIs, InfluxDB, statistical aggregation, and multi-agent deep reinforcement learning, forging an intricate framework for the holistic optimization of 6G networks.

7 Monitoring Data Aggregation: Preliminaries

7.1 What is Data Aggregation?

In the realm of telecom monitoring, data aggregation is a pivotal process integral to the efficient analysis and visualization of vast and intricate datasets. It involves systematically gathering and organizing raw data from diverse sources, transforming it into a structured format that facilitates comprehensive insights. This method is particularly crucial in the telecommunications industry, where copious amounts of data need to be distilled into cohesive statistics for effective decision-making.

Whether applied to a small-scale telecom operation or a large corporation managing terabytes of data, the significance of data aggregation remains paramount. It allows telecom professionals to gain a holistic perspective on various aspects of network performance, customer interactions, and service quality. For example, by aggregating data from different sources, telecom companies can analyse network traffic patterns, identify potential issues, and optimize their infrastructure to enhance overall performance.

In essence, telecom-oriented data aggregation serves as a strategic tool, offering a consolidated view of diverse metrics such as network usage, call quality, and customer feedback. This streamlined approach empowers telecom professionals to make informed decisions, optimize resources, and proactively address challenges, ultimately contributing to the seamless operation of telecommunications networks.

7.2 Types of Data Aggregation

In the telecom sector, data aggregation serves essential roles in both temporal and spatial contexts.

- Temporal aggregation involves analysing data over specific time intervals, enabling the identification of usage trends and patterns in network performance. For instance, telecom operators may use temporal data aggregation to assess call quality metrics hourly, helping them pinpoint time-specific network congestion and optimize service delivery accordingly. This approach aids in understanding how network performance varies throughout the day, week, or month.
- Spatial data aggregation focuses on geographical or network location parameters, facilitating optimization efforts and infrastructure planning based on regional demands. For example, aggregating cellular base stations data helps telecom companies analyse network coverage in specific regions. By understanding where subscribers are concentrated or where coverage is lacking, operators can strategically plan base stations placements to enhance overall service quality.

Data aggregation methods can be categorized as manual or automated, each with distinct use cases.

- Manual aggregation involves human intervention in tasks such as collecting, processing, and summarizing data. This approach is suitable for smaller-scale tasks or instances where data sources are not easily integrated. For instance, manually creating reports by extracting information from different databases and spreadsheets exemplifies the use of manual data aggregation.
- On the other hand, automated data aggregation relies on tools or scripts to handle large-scale data processing efficiently. In the telecom industry, an automated Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) process is commonly used. This process automatically extracts data from various sources, transforms it into a consistent format, and loads it into a central repository for analysis. For real-time analytics, automated aggregation is crucial for processing and responding to data in near-instantaneous fashion. For instance, automated systems can continuously analyse call detail records (CDRs) in real time to detect and address network anomalies as they occur. Real-time data aggregation is particularly vital in the telecom landscape, enabling operators to monitor network performance in real time and respond promptly to critical events. For example, analysing call quality metrics in real time allows for the immediate identification and resolution of network issues, ensuring a seamless user experience. On the other hand, batch data aggregation processes data in scheduled intervals. Nightly batch processes may be used to consolidate and analyse subscriber usage data for historical reporting, trend analysis, and non-real-time decision-making.

Ultimately, the choice between manual and automated aggregation depends on factors such as the scale of data, the frequency of updates, and the complexity of analysis required. Automated systems are generally preferred for their efficiency, accuracy, and ability to handle large volumes of data in the dynamic and fast-paced telecom environment.

7.3 Examples

7.3.1 OpenTelemetry

OpenTelemetry is an open-source observability framework that allows to collect telemetry data from cloud-native applications. It offers tools, APIs, and SDKs to collect and generate metrics, logs, and traces. It supports multiple languages, including Java, Python, Go, Ruby, C++, and Javascript. In the context of telemetry and metric analysis, aggregation serves as a vital technique where a multitude of measurements are consolidated into precise or estimated statistics, capturing the essence of metric events occurring within a specific time window. The OpenTelemetry Protocol (OTLP) emerges as a facilitator for transporting such aggregated metrics, with the OpenTelemetry API offering default aggregations for each instrument. These defaults can be fine-tuned through the utilization of Views. The overarching objective of the OpenTelemetry project is to furnish default aggregations seamlessly compatible with various visualizers and telemetry backends. Unlike request tracing, metrics focus on providing statistical insights in aggregate form. Examples of metric use cases include reporting the total bytes read by a service per protocol type, bytes per request, system call durations, trends in request sizes, CPU or memory usage, average balance values, and real-time counts of active

requests being handled, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of system performance.

7.3.2 MongoDB

Figure 1 Aggregation/Pipeline operation in Mongo database

In MongoDB, data aggregation is a powerful and flexible process that allows users to perform data transformations and computations on collections. Leveraging the Aggregation Framework, MongoDB enables the grouping, filtering, and manipulation of data within a collection to extract meaningful insights. Aggregation pipelines consist of stages, each handling a specific operation, such as matching documents, sorting, and projecting fields. This framework facilitates the creation of complex queries, making it suitable for tasks like summarizing data, generating reports, or deriving key metrics. MongoDB's data aggregation capabilities enhance the efficiency of querying and analysing large datasets, providing a versatile solution for diverse data processing needs within the NoSQL database environment.

8 Background

This section covers background information on data pipelines (Subsection 8.1) and subsequently provide an overview of earlier work related to this area (Subsection 8.2).

8.1 Data Pipelines

8.1.1 Concept

The literature provides varying descriptions of the 'data pipeline' concept, depending on the perspective considered¹. In the following discussion, we present the idea of a data pipeline initially from both a theoretical and a practical standpoint.

From a theoretical standpoint, a data pipeline is conceptualized as a directed acyclic graph (DAG) consisting of a sequence of nodes². These nodes perform operations such as merging and filtering on the data, where the output of one node becomes the input for the next. The DAG begins with at least one source node generating the initial data and concludes with at least one sink node receiving the processed data. Analysing pipelines in this way is often done in mathematical contexts to formally describe and analyse data flows, including node dependencies.

In practical terms, data pipelines typically manifest as software that automates data manipulation and facilitates the movement of data from various source systems to predefined destinations³. Consequently, data pipelines represent digitalized data processing workflows based on a series of programmed scripts or straightforward software tools. Given the escalating significance and intricacy of data processing, data pipelines are now regarded as comprehensive software systems with their own ecosystem, encompassing multiple technologies and software tools⁴. The primary objective of this intricate set of interrelated software components is to enable efficient data processing, transfer, and storage, overseeing all data operations and orchestrating the complete data flow from source to destination.

8.1.2 Generic Architecture

As shown in Figure 1, components of a data pipeline typically include data sources, data processing, data storage, and data sinks, although the internal structure can vary^{5,6}. In this description, we focus on the processing component, which encompasses the fundamental tasks within a data pipeline.

¹ S. Agostinelli, D. Benvenuti, F. De Luzi, A. Marrella, Big data pipeline discovery through process mining: Challenges and research directions, CEUR Workshop Proceedings 2952 (101016835) (2021) 50–55

² M. Drocco, C. Misale, G. Tremblay, M. Aldinucci, A Formal Semantics for Data Analytics Pipelines, Tech. rep. (2017). arXiv:1705.01629

³ A. R. Munappy, J. Bosch, H. H. Olsson, Data Pipeline Management in Practice: Challenges and Opportunities, in: Product-Focused Software Process Improvement. PROFES 2020. Lecture Notes in Computer Science (vol 12562), 2020, pp. 168–184.

⁴ T. Koivisto, Efficient Data Analysis Pipeline, Data Science for Natural Sciences Seminar (2019) 2–5.

⁵ H. Hapke, C. Nelson, Building Machine Learning Pipelines, 1st Edition, O'Reilly, Sebastopol, CA, 2020

⁶ A. R. Munappy, J. Bosch, H. H. Olsson, T. J. Wang, Towards automated detection of data pipeline faults, 27th Asia-Pacific Software Engineering Conference (APSEC) (2020) 346–355.

Figure 2 High-level data pipeline architecture⁷

- **Data Sources:** The origin of any data pipeline lies in its data sources, which can be diverse, including databases, sensors, or text files. Data from these sources are often structured (e.g., relational databases), semi-structured (e.g., emails, web pages), or unstructured (e.g., videos, images).
- **Data Processing:** The central component of a data pipeline is its processing segment, where core tasks such as data ingestion, data preprocessing, and data loading take place. These tasks are referred to as stages throughout this discussion.
 - **Data Ingestion⁸:** Typically, data flow begins with extracting data from sources and importing it into the pipeline. Different methods are applied based on the size and format of the raw data, and ingestion may occur continuously, intermittently, or in batches.
 - **Data Preprocessing⁹:** Once the raw data have entered the pipeline, the objective of data preprocessing is to mold the data into a suitable format for subsequent use. Common preprocessing techniques encompass data integration, cleaning, and transformation. It's important to note that not all preprocessing methods are universally applicable, and their orchestration may vary across use cases. Data integration involves merging and incorporating ingested data, achieved through methods like schema mapping or redundancy removal. Data cleaning addresses data errors and inconsistencies, employing data preparation techniques grouped into categories such as missing value treatment (e.g., imputing or discarding) and noise treatment (e.g., smoothing or polishing). Data transformation is geared towards shaping the data into a form suitable for further processing or application, such as statistical analysis or machine learning models. Typical data preparation techniques for this purpose include

⁷ Foidl, Harald, Valentina Golendukhina, Rudolf Ramler and Michael Felderer. "Data Pipeline Quality: Influencing Factors, Root Causes of Data-related Issues, and Processing Problem Areas for Developers." *J. Syst. Softw.* 207 (2023): 111855.

⁸ T. Hlupić, J. Puniš, An Overview of Current Trends in Data Ingestion and Integration, in: 44th International Convention on Information, Communication and Electronic Technology (MIPRO), 2021, pp. 1265–1270

⁹ B. Malley, D. Ramazzotti, J. T.-y. Wu, Data Pre-processing, in: *Secondary Analysis of Electronic Health Records*, Springer, 2016, Ch. 12, pp. 115–141

binarization, normalization, discretization, dimensionality reduction, numerosity reduction, oversampling, or instance generation.

- **Data Loading:** This task involves loading ingested or preprocessed data into internal storage systems or external destinations.
- **Data Storage:** The internal storage component of the pipeline holds raw, ingested, and processed data, distinguishing between temporary and long-term storage based on pipeline configuration.
- **Data Sinks:** Representing the fourth component, data sinks are destinations where data is ultimately provided, such as other pipelines, various applications, or external data storage systems like data warehouses or databases.

Data processing tasks in a pipeline are supported by monitoring and management tasks.

- **Monitoring:** This set of tasks involves overseeing data quality, all data operations, and controlling pipeline performance. Monitoring utilizes logging mechanisms and alerts to prevent data quality issues and facilitate debugging and recovery from failures.
- **Management:** Primary management tasks include handling data, workflow, and the overall application. Workflow management includes activities related to orchestrating and managing dependencies between different data processing tasks. Data management involves creating and maintaining metadata, data catalogues, and data versioning. Application management encompasses configuring and maintaining software tools that the pipeline relies on, including upgrades and version control.

8.1.3 Data Pipeline Types

Pipelines can be categorized based on various characteristics, with the three most prevalent classifications detailed below.

- **Data Ingestion Strategy:** Data pipelines can be categorized according to their data ingestion frequency. Two primary modes are batch and streaming. Batch-mode pipelines ingest data at fixed intervals (e.g., daily, weekly) or when triggered (e.g., manual execution, data size). Conversely, streaming-mode pipelines continuously ingest data in real-time as it becomes available. Hybrid scenarios, such as the lambda architecture, may employ both ingestion modes simultaneously.
- **Data Processing Method:** Pipelines can also be classified based on the order and application of data processing tasks, often using Extract Transform Load (ETL) or Extract Load Transform (ELT) concepts. ETL pipelines follow a batch-oriented process, involving extracting data, transforming it, and then loading it into data sinks. In contrast, ELT pipelines directly load data into sinks without preprocessing, handling transformations within the data sinks or consuming applications. ELT, a newer concept, is frequently applied in cloud-based environments, delivering rapid data without requiring intermediate storage in the pipeline.
- **Use Case:** Data pipelines serve various purposes and are commonly employed for data movement and preparation, either independently or as part of other applications such as visualization tools, analysis tools, machine learning (ML),

deep learning applications, or data mining. A prevalent use case involves gathering data from diverse sources and centralizing it for further utilization, often termed as data collection pipelines. In the realm of data science, artificial intelligence (AI), or ML applications, data pipelines play a crucial role in preparing data for algorithmic models. Those used in AI-based systems, ML pipelines, or data science projects are typically referred to as data preprocessing pipelines¹⁰.

8.1.4 Data Pipeline Software Stack

In the dynamic landscape of data pipeline orchestration, a diverse set of tools and frameworks, comprising both open-source and proprietary solutions, are pivotal in ensuring efficient and scalable operations. Open-source options include Apache Airflow and Apache Luigi for workflow orchestration, Apache Kafka and RabbitMQ as open-source message brokers, and Apache Flink and Storm for stream processing. Storage is facilitated by open-source solutions like Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) and databases such as MongoDB. Great Expectations, an open-source library, addresses data validation. In contrast, proprietary tools like Azkaban and commercial cloud storage options like Amazon S3 and Google Cloud Storage offer additional choices. The flexibility to choose between open-source (Luigi, Kafka, Flink, MongoDB, Great Expectations, and Airflow) and proprietary (Azkaban) solutions allows tailored configurations, with cloud platforms commonly adopted for enhanced scalability in running and managing data pipelines.

8.2 Related Work

- **Experiences and Guidelines:** A substantial body of literature exists, offering frameworks^{11,12}, guidelines¹³, or architectures¹⁴ to facilitate the development and utilization of data pipelines. While some contributions concentrate on specific application domains, such as manufacturing¹⁵, others take a more generic

¹⁰ S. Biswas, M. Wardat, H. Rajan, The Art and Practice of Data Science Pipelines: A Comprehensive Study of Data Science Pipelines In Theory, In-The-Small, and In-The-Large, in: 44th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE '22), May 21-29, 2022, Pittsburgh, PA, USA, Association for Computing Machinery, 2022, pp. 2091–2103

¹¹ E. Badidi, N. El Neyadi, M. Al Saeedi, F. Al Kaabi, M. Maheswaran, Building a data pipeline for the management and processing of urban data streams, Handbook of Smart Cities: Software Services and Cyber Infrastructure (2018) 379–395.

¹² O. Oleghe, K. Salonitis, A framework for designing data pipelines for manufacturing systems, Procedia CIRP 93 (2020) 724–729.

¹³ R. Tardio, A. Mate, J. Trujillo, An Iterative Methodology for Defining Big Data Analytics Architectures, IEEE Access 8 (2020) 210597–210616.

¹⁴ M. Helu, T. Sprock, D. Hartenstine, R. Venketesh, W. Sobel, Scalable data pipeline architecture to support the industrial internet of things, CIRP Annals 69 (1) (2020) 385–388.

¹⁵ M. Frye, R. H. Schmitt, Structured Data Preparation Pipeline for Machine Learning-Applications in Production, in 17th IMEKO TC 10 and EUROLAB Virtual Conference “Global Trends in Testing, Diagnostics & Inspection for 2030”, 2020, pp. 241–246.

approach¹⁶. Additionally, numerous studies share insights, including lessons learned and challenges, related to engineering data pipelines¹⁷.

- **Quality Aspects:** Comprehensive overviews of the quality aspects of data pipelines are infrequent in research. Existing studies predominantly focus on specific quality characteristics, such as performance and scalability¹⁸, or robustness¹⁹. Notably, in-depth investigations into the quality characteristics of ETL processes²⁰, as a sub-concept of data pipelines, hold considerable relevance.
- **Development and Maintenance Support:** Recent research has emphasized supporting data and software engineers in developing and maintaining data pipelines. Numerous works introduce tools for debugging pipelines²¹. Additionally, various publications strive to enhance pipeline reliability by addressing provenance aspects²².
- **Data Preprocessing:** Beyond general pipeline research, a wealth of studies focuses on data preprocessing within pipelines. This area of research specifically aims to aid in selecting suitable data operators and defining their optimal combinations²³, or even automating the entire creation of preprocessing chains²⁴.

¹⁶ Von Landesberger, D. W. Fellner, R. A. Ruddle, Visualization System Requirements for Data Processing Pipeline Design and Optimization, *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 23 (8) (2017) 2028–2041.

¹⁷ J. Tiezzi, R. Tyler, S. Sharma, Lessons Learned: A Case Study in Creating a Data Pipeline using Twitter's API, in: *Systems and Information Engineering Design Symposium, SIEDS 2020*, IEEE, 2020

¹⁸ G. Van Dongen, D. Van Den Poel, Influencing Factors in the Scalability of Distributed Stream Processing Jobs, *IEEE Access* 9 (2021) 109413–109431.

¹⁹ A. R. Munappy, J. Bosch, H. H. Olsson, On the Trade-off Between Robustness and Complexity in Data Pipelines, in: *International Conference on the Quality of Information and Communications Technology, 2021*, pp. 401–415.

²⁰ Z. E. Akkaoui, A. Vaisman, E. Zim, A Quality-based ETL Design Evaluation Framework, *ICEIS* 1 (2019) 249–257.

²¹ E. K. Rezig, A. Brahmaroutu, N. Tatbul, M. Ouzzani, N. Tang, T. Mattson, S. Madden, M. Stonebraker, Debugging large-scale data science pipelines using dagger, *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment* 13 (12) (2020) 2993–2996

²² S. Grafberger, T. U. Munich, J. Stoyanovich, S. Schelter, Lightweight Inspection of Data Preprocessing in Native Machine Learning Pipelines, in: *Conference on Innovative Data Systems Research (CIDR), 2021*.

²³ V. Desai, H. A. Dinesha, A Hybrid Approach to Data Pre-processing Methods, *IEEE International Conference for Innovation in Technology, INOCON 2020 (2020)* 1–4.

²⁴ J. Giovanelli, B. Bilalli, A. Abell'o, Data pre-processing pipeline generation for AutoETL, *Information Systems* (108) (2022) 101957.

9 Data Aggregation Solutions: A Comparative Study

9.1 Requirements

Data aggregation is an integral part of the target backend system. The requirements thereof can be summarized as follows:

- **Support for All OpenTelemetry Signals:** OpenTelemetry currently gathers telemetry data across three distinct signals: logs, metrics, and traces. Building a robust observability framework requires utilizing all three signals. Therefore, the selected OpenTelemetry backend should be capable of ingesting and visualizing logs, metrics, and traces.
- **Native Integration with OpenTelemetry Semantic Conventions:** In OpenTelemetry, each component of a distributed system is defined as an attribute, represented by a key-value pair. These attributes adhere to OpenTelemetry semantic conventions. For instance, HTTP conventions include attributes like ``http.method`` (HTTP request method), ``http.target`` (full request target), and ``http.scheme`` (URI scheme). The chosen OpenTelemetry backend should natively support storing data in accordance with these conventions. While many observability vendors transform data into proprietary formats, leveraging the full spectrum of OpenTelemetry semantic conventions might be restricted in such cases.
- **Ability to Perform Statistical Aggregates on Trace Data:** Enabling statistical aggregate operations on trace data facilitates the creation of service-centric views. OpenTelemetry allows the creation of custom tags, and when combined with aggregated trace data, it provides a powerful tool for identifying performance issues. For example, one can analyse the error rate and 99th percentile latency for specific custom tags like ``slice_type: urlc``.
- **Open-Source Consideration:** While it is not mandatory for an OpenTelemetry backend to be open source, having open-source status can contribute to a complete open-source solution. Open-source solutions offer greater flexibility, and if self-hosted, alleviate concerns related to data privacy. It is worth noting that OpenTelemetry itself is an open-source standard with robust community support, showcasing the effectiveness of community-driven projects in solving complex engineering problems.

9.2 Comparative Study

Backend database solutions support aggregation features. We therefore compare here two famous open-source databases, namely, MongoDB and InfluxDB in terms of different criteria, including aggregation capabilities.

Table 1 InfluxDB vs MongoDB

Criteria	InfluxDB	MongoDB
OpenTelemetry Compatibility	Compatible	Compatible

Data Model	Time-series database designed for handling time-stamped data. Schema-less, with data organized into measurements, tags, and fields. Well-suited for storing and querying time-series data such as metrics, logs, and events.	Document-oriented database with a flexible schema. Stores data in BSON (Binary JSON) format. Suitable for a wide range of use cases, including general-purpose applications.
Statistical Aggregation features	InfluxDB excels in aggregating time-series data, making it easy to perform statistical calculations over time intervals. It provides a query language called InfluxQL, which includes functions for common statistical operations such as mean, median, sum, count, standard deviation, etc. The downsampling feature allows to aggregate high-resolution data into lower-resolution data over specific time intervals.	MongoDB's aggregation framework includes a variety of operators that can be used for statistical calculations, such as \$sum, \$avg, \$min, \$max, \$stdDevPop, \$stdDevSamp, \$percentile. Although MongoDB's aggregation framework is not specialized for time-series data, it can handle a broad range of aggregation tasks across different types of data models.
Scalability	Designed for high write and query loads in time-series data scenarios. Horizontal scalability is achieved through clustering.	Scales horizontally by sharding data across multiple nodes. Suitable for a broader range of workloads, offering good scalability for various types of applications.
Use Cases	Ideal for applications dealing with monitoring, IoT, and real-time analytics. Suited for scenarios where timestamped data is a primary focus.	Suitable for scenarios where complex, hierarchical data structures are required.
Community and Ecosystem	Strong community support, particularly in the DevOps and monitoring space. A growing ecosystem of integrations and plugins.	Large and active community with extensive documentation. A mature and well-established ecosystem with a wide range of integrations and tools.

9.3 Technical Choice

Opting for InfluxDB over MongoDB for time-series-oriented 6G Key Performance Indicator (KPI) monitoring and statistical aggregation functions offers distinct technical advantages. InfluxDB employs a highly efficient storage engine, TSM (Time-Structured Merge), designed specifically for time-series data. This optimized structure enables faster queries, making it ideal for handling the high-frequency data streams characteristic of 6G networks. Additionally, InfluxDB's use of a tag-based data model, in combination with its native support for precision timestamps, allows for granular data organization and efficient querying. When implementing statistical aggregation functions such as percentile calculations, InfluxDB's native capabilities and indexing mechanisms contribute to accelerated query performance, ensuring timely and accurate analysis of data distribution. Moreover, the implementation of continuous queries and retention policies streamlines data management, facilitating both real-time monitoring and historical analysis. In summary, InfluxDB's technical design tailored for time-series data positions it as a robust and performant choice for the nuanced requirements of 6G KPI monitoring and advanced statistical aggregation functions.

10 Initial Design of Data Aggregation for 6G Self-Optimisation

10.1 The Need of Statistical Data Aggregation

The target 6GENABLERS-AI holoportation use case requires the establishment and orchestration of an ultra-reliable low latency communication (URLLC) slice. To ensure its performance, a typical SLA would state that the slice latency should not exceed a threshold α with a probability higher than π . This translates into learning a decentralized resource provisioning model under empirical complementary cumulative density function (EC-CDF) constraint that reflects the SLA violation rate. Practical SLAs can also be defined in terms of percentiles. In this respect, the infrastructure provider might agree with the tenant of the slice that, e.g., the Q -th percentile of latency, i.e., the value below which $Q\%$ of latency samples are distributed, should be lower than γ . In both SLAs, the reward of the multi-agent deep reinforcement learning (MA-DRL) resource provisioning agents need to include these long-term latency statistics as penalty. In this respect, InfluxDB shall be in charge of aggregating the telemetry data to calculate different statistical metrics.

10.2 Aggregation Functions

10.2.1 EC-CDF

The empirical complementary cumulative density function is a statistical concept used to describe the distribution of a set of empirical data. It is often employed in data analysis and non-parametric statistics. The EC-CDF provides information about the probability that a random variable is greater than a certain value. Mathematically, the EC-CDF is constructed from empirical data points. Given a data with observations $(x_1, \dots, x_n)$, the EC-CDF at a specific value γ is calculated as the proportion of data points greater than or equal to γ . In mathematical terms it is defined as,

$$F_{\text{EC-CDF}}(x) = \frac{\text{Number of observations } \geq x}{\text{Total number of observations}}$$

This function provides a step-wise representation of the cumulative probability distribution of the data, allowing for a visual understanding of the data's spread and characteristics. The complementary aspect refers to the probability that the random variable is greater than a given value, providing complementary information to the standard cumulative density function (CDF).

A python template to compute the EC-CDF from InfluxDB is depicted in Figure 3.

```

# Set your InfluxDB connection details
host = 'your_influxdb_host'
port = 8086
database = 'your_database_name'
measurement = 'your_measurement_name'

# Connect to InfluxDB
client = InfluxDBClient(host=host, port=port, database=database)

# Query data from InfluxDB
query = 'SELECT "your_field" FROM "{}".format(measurement)'
result = client.query(query)
points = result.get_points()

# Extract values from the query result
values = [point['your_field'] for point in points]

# Calculate EC-CDF
sorted_values = np.sort(values)
ec_cdf = np.arange(1, len(sorted_values) + 1) / len(sorted_values)

# Plot EC-CDF
plt.step(sorted_values, 1 - ec_cdf, label='EC-CDF')
plt.xlabel('Values')
plt.ylabel('Empirical Complementary CDF')
plt.title('Empirical Complementary Cumulative Density Function (EC-CDF)')
plt.legend()
plt.show()

```

Figure 3 Python template for calculating EC-CDF from InfluxDB.

10.2.2 Percentile

The Q -th percentile is a statistical measure that indicates the value below which a given percentage (Q) of observations in a dataset falls. It is a way to divide a dataset into hundredths, with the Q -th percentile representing the point below which $Q\%$ of the data falls. The Q -th percentile is often denoted as P_Q .

Mathematically, to find the Q -th percentile of a dataset, you first arrange the data in ascending order. Then, you locate the position in the ordered list given by the formula:

$$\text{Position} = \left(\frac{Q}{100} \right) \times (\text{Number of Observations} + 1)$$

If the position is a whole number, the Q -th percentile is the value at that position. If the position is not a whole number, you typically interpolate between the two closest values in the dataset to determine the Q -th percentile. The Q -th percentile is a valuable measure in statistics as it helps to understand the distribution of data and identify values that are representative of certain percentiles in a dataset. For example, the median is the 50th percentile, the first quartile (Q_1) is the 25th percentile, and the third quartile (Q_3) is the 75th percentile.

A python template to calculate the Q -th percentile from InfluxDB is shown in Figure 4.

```

from influxdb import InfluxDBClient
import numpy as np

# Set your InfluxDB connection details
host = 'your_influxdb_host'
port = 8086
database = 'your_database_name'
measurement = 'your_measurement_name'

# Q-th percentile you want to calculate (e.g., 75th percentile)
q_percentile = 75

# Connect to InfluxDB
client = InfluxDBClient(host=host, port=port, database=database)

# Query data from InfluxDB
query = 'SELECT "your_field" FROM "{}".format(measurement)'
result = client.query(query)
points = result.get_points()

# Extract values from the query result
values = [point['your_field'] for point in points]

# Calculate Q-th percentile
qth_percentile_value = np.percentile(values, q_percentile)

print(f"{q_percentile}-th Percentile Value: {qth_percentile_value}")

```

Figure 4 Python template for computing the Q -th percentile from InfluxDB.

10.3 Monitoring, Aggregation and Decision Closed Loop Design

As depicted in Figure 5, the process begins with an Open Telemetry metric collector that captures telemetry data generated by various components in a distributed system. This telemetry data, encompassing performance metrics and other relevant information, is then directed towards observability APIs. These APIs facilitate seamless integration with monitoring and analytics tools. The collected data is subsequently stored in InfluxDB, a time-series database, where it undergoes aggregation to distil meaningful insights. The aggregated data serves as a crucial input for a Resource Allocation Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) agent. This intelligent agent employs machine learning techniques to make informed decisions regarding resource allocation based on the observed patterns and performance metrics. The DRL agent triggers scaling actions to dynamically adjust resources, optimizing the overall system efficiency. One of the outcomes of this scaling process is the adaptation of the holoportation app Virtual Network Function (VNF), which undergoes scaling operations as dictated by the DRL agent. The entire closed-loop system is orchestrated to achieve automated and adaptive resource management, enhancing the scalability and performance of the holoportation app through continuous feedback from the metric collector and the iterative decision-making process of the DRL agent.

Figure 5 Monitoring, aggregation, and decision closed loop.

11 Conclusion

In conclusion, this deliverable has encapsulated a comprehensive exploration of data aggregation methodologies for 6G network optimisation, anchored in intelligent telemetry. The report has navigated through foundational concepts, drawing practical examples from OpenTelemetry and MongoDB, and delved into literature on data pipelines and architecture. By identifying key requirements and conducting a rigorous comparative analysis, the document substantiates the selection of InfluxDB as the preferred aggregation database. Emphasizing the critical role of statistical aggregation, it has introduced EC-CDF and percentile functions with practical Python code snippets extracted from InfluxDB.

Finally, the deliverable has unveiled the initial design of a closed-loop system, intricately connecting essential components like the metric collector, observability API, InfluxDB-based aggregation, resource scaling agent, and the holoportation app VNF. Beyond addressing current optimisation needs, this framework has laid the groundwork for 6G ultra-automation and optimisation.